

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19657473>

ANNOTATION

This article analyzes the role of artificial intelligence technologies in teaching foreign languages, their impact and effectiveness on the educational process. The article also considers the possibility of individualizing the language learning process using artificial intelligence-based platforms and applications. The article also highlights the advantages and existing challenges of AI technologies in the modern educational environment.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, foreign languages, educational technology, translation, online education, innovation, language learning, AI.

INTRODUCTION

In today's process of globalization, the issue of learning and teaching foreign languages becomes more relevant. Knowledge of foreign languages is an important factor for effective communication in modern society, the development of international cooperation and success in scientific and professional activities. At the same time, the accelerated development of information and communication technologies brings new opportunities to the education system.

In particular, the emergence and widespread use of artificial intelligence technologies fundamentally change the process of teaching foreign languages. With the help of artificial intelligence-based programs and platforms, it is possible to organize education tailored to the individual characteristics of students, level of knowledge and speed of learning. This will not only improve teaching effectiveness, but also develop pupil's skills for independent study.

Therefore, the study of the role and significance of artificial intelligence in the teaching of foreign languages, the analysis of its advantages and existing problems is one of the actual scientific tasks. It is these aspects that will be covered extensively in this article.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

The issue of the use of artificial intelligence in teaching foreign languages has been widely studied in recent years by a large number of domestic and foreign scientists. Scientific research in this direction shows the positive impact of AI technologies on the educational process.

As one of the leading scientists, **John McCarthy** was the founder of the concept of artificial intelligence, whose work later provided a theoretical framework for the use of AI in education. Also, *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach*, written by **Stuart Russell** and **Peter Norvig**, extensively covers the basic principles and areas of application of artificial intelligence, which is also an important resource for the education system.

Also important are Stephen Krashen's theories **on the use of technology in language learning**. While he emphasized the importance of the natural environment and intelligible input in language acquisition, modern AI tools can artificially create exactly that environment.

And recent studies have recognized artificial intelligence-based applications such as automatic translation systems, speech recognition programs, and interactive platforms (such as chatbots) as effective tools for language learning. In this regard, many scientific articles have noted the possibility of providing an individual approach using AI, the ability to quickly identify and analyze students' errors.

Local researchers also widely cover the digitalization of the education system and the introduction of innovative technologies. The ability to improve the quality of education by integrating artificial intelligence into the educational process is emphasized in their work.

In general, the analysis of the available literature shows that artificial intelligence has great potential in the teaching of foreign languages, which serves to increase the effectiveness of teaching. At the same time, it is necessary to further develop the methodological framework for the effective application of these technologies.

The use of artificial intelligence technologies in the teaching of foreign languages is significantly improving the educational process. Modern AI systems will allow you to determine the level of knowledge of students, analyze their mistakes and form individual curricula. This will help them achieve more effective results compared to traditional teaching methods.

First, artificial intelligence-based applications increase interactivity in language learning. For example, with chatbots, learners can practice in close to real-world communication environments. Such systems establish constant communication with the user, quickly answer his questions and serve to develop speech skills.

Second, the possibility of individualizing the educational process with the help of AI technologies expands. Because each student's level of knowledge, ability, and speed of learning is different, artificial intelligence systems provide them with customized materials and assignments. This increases the level of mastery of students' knowledge.

Third, automatic translation and speech recognition technologies are an important tool in language learning. These systems allow for fast and accurate translation of texts, pronunciation checking, and correction of errors. As a result, students will have the opportunity to work on themselves.

Also, artificial intelligence-based platforms will create convenience for teachers. They automate the process of tracking, grading, and analyzing student performance. This allows teachers to save time and improve the quality of education.

However, there are also some problems with the use of artificial intelligence. In particular, over-reliance on technology, reduced human factor, data security and privacy issues are relevant. This is why it is important to use AI technologies wisely and balancedly.

In general, artificial intelligence is an important tool for introducing innovative approaches to the teaching of foreign languages, the effective organization of the educational process and improving the level of knowledge of students.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the use of artificial intelligence technologies in the teaching of foreign languages takes the educational process to a new level. AI-based tools play an important role in the development of their knowledge and skills, organizing effective teaching taking into account the individual characteristics of students. Also, these technologies increase the interactivity of the educational process, allowing students to learn independently.

At the same time, there are some problems in the introduction of artificial intelligence into the education system, which need to be overcome. In particular, the issues of insufficient technical infrastructure, the level of digital skills of teachers and information security are relevant.

Taking into account the above circumstances, the following proposals can be put forward:

The necessary technical base for the introduction of modern AI technologies in educational institutions;

Improving teachers' skills in the use of artificial intelligence;

Widespread use of interactive platforms and applications based on AI in teaching foreign languages;

Development and implementation of individual areas of education for students; to ensure data security and to form a culture of information use.

As a final conclusion, it can be said that the rational and effective use of artificial intelligence technologies serves to significantly improve the quality of teaching foreign languages and will become an integral part of the modern education system.

Recommendations:

In order to ensure the effective use of artificial intelligence technologies in teaching foreign languages, the following recommendations can be made:

1. step-by-step introduction of artificial intelligence-based platforms and applications into the education process;
2. organization of special training and seminars for teachers on the use of AI technologies;
3. the extensive use of AI in the development of individualized curricula tailored to students' level of knowledge;
4. the use of interactive methods in the study of foreign languages, including chatbots and speech recognition systems;
5. providing educational institutions with modern technical means and reliable Internet;
6. strengthening information security and personal data protection measures when using artificial intelligence;
7. orient students to independent learning and develop skills in the proper use of AI tools;

to develop and support local AI programs that are aligned with the national education system.

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